

The Behaviour of Filament-Wound GRP Tubes under Impulsive Loads

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ABSTRACT

This paper will present results of the various researches taking place at the moment on the response of filament-wound GRP tubes to impulsive loads.

- a) Radial expansion and vibration of short tubes initiated by radial electro-magnetic loads acting on an aluminium driver.
- b) Axial symmetric impact on filament-wound tubes using an electro-magnetically driven driver.
- c) Axial non-symmetric impact on filament-wound tubes.
- d) Impact of non-deformable projectiles on GRP tubes.

A discussion of the phenomenological aspects of the fracture of the specimens, as well as details of the various instrumentation, will be given.

